

First Steps towards Sustainable-by-Design Anchoring Systems for Floating Offshore Wind

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ABSTRACT: The Horizon Europe research project TAILWIND aims to advance station-keeping system technologies for floating offshore wind farms. This paper marks the first steps in the project putting forward economic, environmental, and technological key performance indicators to assist the selection of anchoring systems. Scenarios in terms of location, soil profile, and floater are defined. Anchor loading histories are obtained through coupled load simulations and used to design typical anchors. Key performance indicators describing three sustainability aspects – economic, environmental, and technological – are proposed to assess the industrial feasibility of each anchoring systems. The result of the study is twofold. On the one hand, sustainability key performance indicators that can guide the selection of anchoring technologies for future floating offshore wind development are proposed. On the other hand, a guidance to the most promising anchoring systems for further development via experimental testing and numerical modelling within the TAILWIND project is provided.

Keywords: Floating offshore wind, sustainable-by-design technologies, anchors

1 INTRODUCTION

TAILWIND is a four-year research project on station-keeping systems for floating offshore wind (FOW) turbines funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme. The project mandate is to advance anchoring systems and mooring line technologies while exploring the impact of these on society and environment to create sustainable-by-design station-keeping systems.

In the last decades, many anchoring systems for temporary or stationary floating offshore oil and gas (O&G) structures have been deployed. Anchors for FOW pose new challenges such as the requirement of diffused anchor points, as opposed to one-off O&G structures, and the need for solutions that combine

scalability, social acceptance, and low environmental impact. Recent state-of-the-art reviews on anchoring system for FOW highlight the need of methodological and technical innovations to meet the future market demand (Cerfontaine et al., 2023; Catapult, 2024; Xu et al., 2023).

The goal of this paper is to develop a framework that enables the selection of a sustainable-by-design anchor for a given FOW scenario, which accounts for societal environmental, technological and economic impact. In the following, the design load for five scenarios are first established and typical anchors are designed to sustain them. Each anchoring solution is then ranked by different metrics to conduct an industrial feasibility assessment.

2 SCENARIOS

Five scenarios were selected for the anchor design assessment, which vary in reference location, floater and mooring types, and mooring material (Table 1). Preliminary simulations were undertaken to determine the design loads associated to each scenario, whose details can be found in the report TAILWIND (2024a).

2.1 Reference locations and soil parameters

Reference locations define the water depth, soil profile and metocean conditions. In TAILWIND two reference locations (RLs) were selected for the load simulations: RL1 – Utsira Nord with 265 m water depth, and RL2 – Provence Grand Large with 100 m water depth (see Figure 1). The soil profiles were based on cone penetration test results of the sites found in literature (e.g. Lunne et al., 2006) but were simplified to keep the analysis distinguished between sandy and clayey soil. RL1 has three normally consolidated clay layers with soil sensitivity, $S_r = 3$, adhesion factor, $\alpha = 0.5$, plasticity index, $I_p = 20\%$. Its profile in terms of triaxial compression undrained shear strength, s_{uc} , and cone resistance, q_t , is given in Figure 2a). RL2 has three sand layers with interface friction angle, $\delta = 29^\circ$, and friction angle, $\phi = 28^\circ, 33^\circ$, and 37° for the three layers respectively. Its profile in terms of relative density, D_r , and cone resistance, q_t , is given in Figure 2b).

2.2 Load simulations

Coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulations using metocean conditions of RL1 and RL2 with the software OrcaFlex were run with the IEA Wind 15 MW reference wind turbine (Evan et al., 2020). The anchor was considered as a pinned support.

Figure 1. Mean water depth map taken from EMODnet (European Commission, 2024) with indication of Reference Location 1 (RL1) – Utsira Nord – and Reference Location 2 (RL2) – Provence Grand Large.

Figure 2. Principal soil properties of a) RL1; b) RL2.

The following two FOW platforms and mooring systems were simulated (see Figure 3):

1. Semi-submersible (Semi-sub) of the project partner NAUTILUS featuring semi-taut system with 4 hybrid chain and polyester mooring lines;
2. Tension Leg Buoy (TLB) of the project partner TECNALIA featuring taut mooring system with hybrid steel and dyneema mooring lines and 12 anchors distributed over 6 mooring line directions;

The floaters' details are given in TAILWIND (2024a). The anchor design tension, T_d , and the loading angle relative to horizontal at touch down are given in Table 2.1. The T_d of Scenario 7 is larger than that of Scenario 3, which was not expected being RL2 in the Mediterranean and RL1 in the North Sea. This is the result of shallower water in RL2 that requires lower floater excursion limits and therefore stiffer moorings. A concurrent reason is that the wave length in RL2 nearly matches the floater's diagonal length, causing significant pitching and consequently high peak loads reason. The TLB loads are very large as it is a mooring stabilised system whose mooring concept is yet to be optimised in the TAILWIND project. They represent upper bound anchor loads for a 15 MW FOW turbine. Scenarios 3b and 10b are slight modifications of Scenarios 3 and 10 to allow for shared anchors. The load on the shared anchors was calculated vectorially after Fontana et al. (2018). Note that the load of shared anchors (scenarios 3b and 10b) is only slightly smaller than or even exceeds that of equivalent single anchors.

Figure 3. Floating platform adopted for the load simulations: a) Semi-submersible (Semi-sub) – four anchors and four mooring lines; b) Tension leg buoy (TLB) – Twelve anchors and twelve mooring lines over six directions.

Table 1. Summary of design tension T_a and loading angle relative to horizontal at touch down β .

Platform	Site / Mooring concept	Scenario	T_a [MN] / β [deg]
Semi-sub	RL1 / Semi-taut	3	12.2 / 6.0
		3b	11.7 / 7.6
	RL2 / Semi-taut	7	20.3 / 9.6
TLB	RL1 / Taut	10	35.2 / 23.7
		10b	38.7 / 13.6

This contrasts in part with previous similar studies where the loads of shared anchors were seen to decrease compared to equivalent single anchors (Fontana et al., 2018; Catapult, 2024). This discrepancy can be ascribed to mooring type – the vertical component of taut and semi-taut systems on a shared anchor adds up – and mooring line layout and orientation – four mooring line directions each spaced 90° have less load compensation potential than three mooring line directions each spaced 120°. As shown is Section 4 however, shared anchoring systems can still be advantageous over single anchoring systems.

3 ANCHOR DESIGN ASSESSMENT

The anchor design preliminary assessment was limited to the five DNV certifiable anchor types shown in Figure 4. Conventional design methods and ULS material factors stated in DNV (2021) were adopted. Table 2 summarises the anchor dimensions for all five scenarios. It can be observed that:

- Not all five anchors were suitable to each scenario. For instance, gravity anchor in normally

Figure 4. Anchor types considered in the assessment.

- consolidated clay (RL1) or fluke anchor for taut moorings (Scenario 10) were excluded;
 - As expected, suction anchors are not efficient in sandy soil (RL2) due to the aspect ratio constraint – embedded length to diameter smaller than one – in coarse grained materials;
 - Given the dimensions of plate anchors – surface of exceeding 50 m² – and the proof loading required for fluke anchors for the large design tensions involved, installation of fluke and plate anchors may not be currently feasible;
 - Gravity anchors were assumed to be iron ore filled steel boxes. Other solutions involving precast concrete or clump weights may be more efficient but were not considered as too design-specific.
- The reader is referred to TAILWIND (2024b) for complete explanations on the design procedures.

4 INDUSTRIAL FEASIBILITY

The main TAILWIND proposition is that social, economic, environmental, and technological sustainability must be fulfilled for a given anchor to be industrially feasible.

Table 2. Overview of the anchor dimensions designed for each scenario, see TAILWIND(2024a) for full details.

Scenario	Anchor Type	Diam. [m]	Width [m]	Length [m]	Wall thick. [m]	Dry Weight [Te]	Dry Ballast weight [Te]
3	Suction anchor	5	-	16.5	0.04	97	-
	Pile Anchor	3.4	-	32	0.05	132	-
	Plate Anchor	-	5.5	8.5	0.1	37	-
	Fluke Anchor (MK6)	-	8	9	-	35	-
3b	Suction anchor, shared	5	-	17	0.04	100	-
	Pile anchor, shared	3.4	-	29	0.05	120	-
7	Suction Anchor	12	-	11	0.06	287	-
	Pile anchor	3.4	-	24	0.05	99	-
	Gravity Anchor	-	20	20	-	727	7982
	Plate Anchor	-	5.2	8.1	0.1	33	-
	Fluke Anchor (MK6)	-	8	9	-	40	-
10	Suction Anchor	7.5	-	23	0.05	249	-
	Pile anchor	4.3	-	46	0.05	246	-
	Plate Anchor	-	8	12.4	0.1	79	-
10b	Suction Anchor, shared	8	-	23.5	0.05	273	-
	Pile anchor, shared	4.3	-	50	0.05	341	-

In the following sections, key performance indicators (KPI) that express the proposed four dimensions of sustainability are described. KPI estimations are based on a floating wind development with 33 turbines. The number of anchors per turbine is reduced by 20% for Scenario 10b – 9.6 anchors per turbine for Scenario 10b instead of 12 for Scenario 10 – and by 40% for Scenario 3b – 2.4 anchors per turbine for Scenario 3b instead of 4 for Scenario 3. These are conservative estimations based on layout simulations for 33 turbines. As a mean of comparison, the only shared anchors installed so far in the FOW industry is Hywind Tampen which features 1.7 anchors per turbine for a 3-line mooring system (Catapult, 2024).

4.1 Social sustainability

Local communities and supply chains must profit from the production and deployment of FOW technology. An analysis of regional socio-economic development including spatial organization of labour at both international and inter-regional scales would be necessary to tackle social sustainability. In this initial study, a simplified approach was used: the fabrication, logistics and installation costs of anchors for RL1 produced in three different locations - China, Norway, and Spain – was compared. Spain was selected as the best compromise between supporting the European supply chain while keeping down costs and emissions. This analysis was limited to RL1 but Spain as production country was reasonably assumed also for RL2. Note that also according to the global supply chain study ERM (2024), Spain is the fabrication

location with the lowest cost for a destination port in Stavanger.

4.2 Economic sustainability

The costs of all relevant project phases must be optimised to ensure anchors supply at scale. This is expressed by KPI_1 – Cost of fabrication, installation, and logistics – and KPI_2 – Site investigation effort. A cost model provided by the project partner Subsea 7 is used to estimate KPI_1. Logistics comprises the cost of transportation and marshalling with assumptions on type of equipment and timing for moving, loading, and offloading operations as well as storage. Installation costs are estimated selecting realistic vessel in terms of day rates and number of vessel days considering also the necessary equipment to install the anchors. The site investigation effort is a function of the anchor depth and the number of anchor locations. The latter is obviously relevant only when shared anchors are considered in the scenario.

4.3 Environmental sustainability

The industrial environment during anchor fabrication and transportation, and the marine environment during anchor installation and operational lifetime must be protected. This is expressed by KPI_3 – Material sustainability – and KPI_4 – Impact on marine environment. KPI_3 is expressed as a function of material efficiency – ratio between design tension and dry tonnage – and the decommissioning and recycling potential. KPI_4 is a function of the disturbance to benthic zone and the installation noise.

4.4 Technological sustainability

A given anchor must have been through enough tests and offshore deployments so that the risk of installation refusal and failure during operation is low. KPI_5 was devised to express this principle and is a function of the general technology readiness level and the specific installation risk associated with FOW development. For instance, installation experience of plate anchors does not exist in sand, which results in a relatively small KPI_5 for such systems.

4.5 Results

An evaluation matrix for each scenario is obtained by using the Weighted Sum Method, which is a formal multi-criteria decision analysis technique (Kolios et al., 2016), through the KPIs described above. To articulate and diversify the final scoring, four sets of weightings were defined:

- Set 1 – All weights equal equal;
- Set 2 – Focus on economic sustainability;
- Set 3 – Focus on environmental sustainability;
- Set 4 – Focus on technological sustainability.

The evaluation matrix of Scenario 3 and 3b is shown in Table 3 as example. It is seen that shared suction anchors have consistently the best scoring across the different weighting sets. Pile anchors score poorly mostly out of environmental reasons – installation noise and low decommissioning and recycling potential. Impact-driven piles were assumed in this

Table 3. Evaluation matrix for Scenario 3 and 3b.

Anchor type	Weighting			
	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Set 4
Suction anchor	0.80	0.68	0.75	0.90
Pile anchor	0.48	0.49	0.29	0.74
Plate anchor	0.68	0.67	0.77	0.53
Fluke anchor	0.66	0.73	0.68	0.53
Shared suction anchor	0.87	0.92	0.87	0.88
Shared pile anchor	0.64	0.79	0.43	0.74

analysis. The adoption of vibratory-driven piles would so well when the focus is on technological sustainability. increase the score. Plate and fluke score poorly for Weighting Set 4. Even though these two anchors, and especially fluke anchors, have been widely used and feature therefore high technology readiness level, the current lack of experience and equipment suitable for large scale FOW developments, prevent them to excel despite their notably high geotechnical performance. An overview of the average scoring over the four weighting sets and associated standard deviation of each anchor in all five scenarios is given in Figure 5. The bars of Scenario 3 and 3b reflect what was observed in Table 3 – i.e. shared suction anchor scores best and is rather stable across the weighting sets while piles are penalised for their environmental impact. In Scenario 7, plate and fluke anchors score best but their standard deviation is high due the technical uncertainty in installation in sand for plate and of lack of capable vessels for fluke.

Figure 5. Industrial feasibility overview. Bars: average scoring of all four weighting sets normalised with the highest score in each scenario; Black line: standard deviation.

Had shared piles be considered in Scenario 7, they would likely reach the scoring of plate and fluke anchors. Furthermore, as expected, plate anchors score best where the loads are largest (Scenario 10 and 10b) due to their high geotechnical bearing performance.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This contribution proposes a first attempt to implement the sustainable-by-design principle for floating offshore wind anchor selection. Such principle integrates the quantitative consideration of sustainability aspects along with typical design criteria such as safety and cost effectiveness towards the selection of the most suitable anchor given a scenario in terms of location, floater, and mooring system. The paper shows how KPIs that quantify societal, economic, environmental and technological sustainability aspects can be defined to assist the selection of anchors in five different scenarios. The TAILWIND partners will use the presented analysis to select the anchoring systems to further investigate both numerically and physically.

The main challenge encountered when creating the evaluation matrix was the quantification of KPIs for environmental sustainability. Future research activities on this topic should include: (i) improved ways to define and evaluate the KPIs, for instance by using dedicated environmental studies or probabilistic analyses and (ii) more sophisticated multi-criterial decision analysis techniques such as the order of preference by similarity to the ideal solution (Kolios et al., 2016).

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DISCLAIMER

By presenting this approach, the authors do not intend to recommend using any particular anchor. It should be emphasised that the final anchor selection is a function of the specifics of the given FOW development.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Authors from NGI, Subsea 7, University of Southampton, and DTU: Methodology, Writing Original draft, Funding Acquisition.

Other Authors: Reviewing and Editing, Funding Acquisition.

REFERENCES

- Catapult (2024). Floating offshore wind anchor review.
- DNV (2021). DNV-ST-0119 Floating wind turbine structures.
- European Commission (2024). *European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)*, Available at: <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>, accessed: 06/12/2024.
- ERM (2024). Global Supply Chain Study. Available at: <https://www.norwep.com/market-intelligence/global-supply-chain-study>, accessed: 15/12/2024.
- Evan, G., Rinker, J., Sethuraman, L., Zahle, F., Anderson, B., Barter, G., Abbas, N., Meng, F., Bortolotti, P., Skrzypinski, W., Scott, G., Feil, R., Bredmose, H., Dykes, K., Shields, M., Allen, C., and Viselli, A. (2020). Definition of the IEA 15-Megawatt Offshore Reference Wind. Golden, National Renewable Energy Laboratory. NREL/TP-5000-75698.
- Fontana, C., Hallowell, S., Arwade, S., DeGroot, D., Landon, M., Aubeny, C., Diaz, B., Myers, B., Ozmutlu, S. (2018). Multiline anchor force dynamics in floating offshore wind turbines. *Wind Energy*, 21, 1177-1190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2222>.
- Lunne, T., Long, M., & Uzielli, M. (2006). Characterisation and engineering properties of Troll clay. *Proceedings of the Second International Workshop on Characterisation and Engineering Properties of Natural Soils*, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1201/NOE0415426916>.
- Kolios, A., Mytilinou, V., Lozano-Minguez, E., & Salonitis, K. (2016). A Comparative Study of Multiple-Criteria Decision-Making Methods under Stochastic Inputs. *Energies* 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9070566>.
- TAILWIND (2024a). Deliverable 1.1 – Project design basis.
- TAILWIND (2024b). Deliverable 3.1 – Sustainable anchor concepts.
- Xu, H., Rui, S., Shen, K., Jiang, L., Zhang, H., Teng, L. (2023). Shared mooring systems for offshore floating wind farms: A review. *Energy Reviews*, 3, 100063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enrevrev.2023.100063>